

ELECTRICITY INDUSTRY. GENERAL CONCEPTS ABOUT ENERGY SAVING.

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Abstract: *Nowadays, the efficient use of energy resources is given great importance in all countries of the world. Such a situation can be explained by the increase in investment expenditure for the extraction and processing of fuel and energy resources, the increase in the consumption of additional labor resources and materials. This article provides information about the electricity industry and energy efficiency.*

Keywords : *Energy, synthetic rubber, power plants (PP), hydroelectric plants (HEP), energy chain, floating power plants (FPP).*

This network has an important influence on the location of the industry on the scale of the country or economic region. This effect occurs in two directions. The first direction is the transmission of electrical energy over long distances. This allows the development of industry in all regions of the country. The second direction is to locate energy-intensive industries in areas that produce abundant and cheap electricity. Industries that require a lot of electricity include the production of titanium, aluminum, magnesium, synthetic fiber, synthetic rubber, and synthetic ammonia. One ton of titanium requires 60,000 kWh of electricity, 26,000 kWh for magnesium, and 20,000 kWh for aluminum production. So, if energy costs make up the main part of the cost of the manufactured product, such production is called energy-intensive production. Industries that require less electricity include ferrous metallurgy (except electrometallurgy), soda and paper production, machine building, furniture, plywood, and textile industries. The following factors are taken into account when locating the electric power industry: a) fuel and hydropower

resources; b) technical progress in the production and transmission of electric energy; c) location of the consumer. The main feature of this network is that the production of electricity coincides with its consumption. Low cost of produced energy is of great importance for the national economy of the country or the economy of the economic region. The cost of electricity depends on the cost of extraction and transportation of fuel used in power plants. Therefore, when choosing a place for the construction of power stations, the costs of transporting fuel and delivering electricity to the consumer are taken into account. If the cost of transporting fuel is higher than the cost of transmitting electricity, the power plant is built close to the fuel source, and if energy transmission is expensive, it is built close to the consumer. In some cases, in areas where electricity is in high demand, power plants are built to run on imported fuel. Currently, the distance that can be used to transmit electricity is increasing year by year. The fact that electricity can be transmitted over long distances makes it an advantage over other types of fuel. This allows the following to be implemented: — full and comprehensive use of local types of fuel; — to build large and powerful power stations; - to use electricity in all sectors of the economy. Electricity is produced in thermal power plants (PP), hydroelectric power plants (HPP), thermal power plants (TPP), nuclear power plants (NPP) and non-conventional power generation stations.

More than 70 percent of the electricity produced in the world is produced in thermal power plants. They are built much faster and cheaper. Their capacity can be increased from 6 million kW. In the construction of thermal power plants, electrical resources, production and transport conditions, construction costs and terms, and operation of the station are assumed. In most thermal power plants, heat energy is produced along with electricity. Such power stations are called thermal power stations (TPS). In them, the water heated during the production of electricity is sent to heat greenhouses, buildings and production facilities. But heated water can only be sent up to 20 km away, so TPSs are mostly built near industrial plants and in large cities. Russia is the world leader in this field. Hydroelectric power plants (HPPs) generate energy based on the power of continuously flowing water. That is why the

price of electricity produced in them is low. Hydroelectric power plants are a set of structures and equipment that convert water flow energy into electrical energy. The continuous flow of water in plains and foothill rivers is created mainly due to dams. The hydroelectric power plant is located next to the dam, or inside, in some cases below the dam. In mountain rivers, derivation is often created by hydroelectric power stations. The HPP building is placed far below the dam, in some places underground. The flow of the river is regulated by the construction of reservoirs in order to obtain energy throughout the year. When large hydroelectric power stations are built, river water is used for transportation and irrigation purposes, as well as for water supply.

Such structures are called hydrocells. Hydroelectric power generation, land irrigation, water supply to farms and population, development of shipbuilding and fishing. Currently, a new type of hydroelectric power plants (HPp) is being built. They are built due to uneven use of electricity in power systems. HPPs collect (accumulate) the energy produced by other hydropower plants, where they use excess electricity (for example, at night) in systems built to pump water from the station to a reservoir above it. When the demand for electricity increases, the water in this basin is released, and due to the generated current, electricity is generated in HPP. Several cascades of power stations can be created on one river. It creates the best opportunities for multiple use of water resources. For example, 19 power stations were built on the Chirchik River and 12 on the Volga River. 65% of hydropower resources are in developing countries, but their utilization rate is low. The level of use of hydropower resources is very high in the USA, Russia and Norway. 99.5% of electricity in Norway is produced by hydroelectric power stations. Here, the main part of hydroelectric power plants (more than 200) is located underground. 20 percent of the electricity produced in the world is produced in hydroelectric power plants. Nuclear power plants produce 15-17 percent of the world's electricity. NPPs are built in places that do not have their own energy source and where fuel is expensive, but electricity is in high demand. Its raw material is uranium. NPPs are now built in more than 30 countries. The first NPP was built in

Russia (Obninsk NPP). The USA, France, Japan, Germany, and Russia are the leaders in the production of electricity at NPPs, more than 70 percent of electricity in France is produced at NPPs. Power plants operating on the basis of non-conventional energy sources include solar power plants (SPP), wind power plants (WPP), geothermal power plants (Gpp), floating power plants (FPP), offshore current power plants (CPP) and others.

The energy chain is the path of the energy flow from the primary energy resources to the transmission of energy to the consumer and its use. For example, electricity is obtained as a result of extraction of gas from the ground, transmission of heat to the power plant through pipes and burning, this is the way of electric energy until it is transmitted to the consumer through electric networks and consumed in the production of products. Energy saving is a set of measures for effective use of energy resources. For example, an event aimed at saving electricity in production. The amount of energy is the amount of energy used in the production of a product or in the performance of a task. The term "energy volume" is currently considered as an indicator of the relative consumption of more energy in relation to a monetary unit (national income, cost of production). Efficient use of energy - social, political, financial constraints, environment, ecology, etc. to achieve economic benefits as a result of distribution of energy to consumers in the most optimal way and use in production, taking into account Energy saving is an activity aimed at reducing energy consumption in production. For example, an event aimed at reducing power consumption in electric motors.

Passive energy saving. Heat insulation - protection of electrical technical, electrical mechanical and electrical thermal devices from unnecessary heat exchange with the external environment, i.e. reducing heat loss. Heat transfer - transfer of heat through air and gas medium from parts of electrical technical, electrical mechanical and electrical thermal and heat devices. Heat conduction is the transfer of heat from one part to another in parts of electrical technical, electrical mechanical and electrical thermal devices that are in mutual contact. Energy-saving devices - that is, devices that use heat and electricity at the lowest values.

Energy-saving devices are electrical devices that operate in the operating mode with the highest useful efficiency and power coefficient, regardless of the level of load during their use.

Active saving of energy in working energy and energy-consuming devices. Consequently, implementation of heating and air conditioning with the help of air conditioners through certain programs and technical means. Optimal load management - optimal management of energy consumption in industrial equipment using special devices depending on the load level. Adjustment of loads - is carried out with the help of auxiliary devices and tools in industrial installations. Limiting the switching process - limiting the time of transition of the working mechanisms of industrial devices from one operating mode to another based on a special device and software control.

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